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What Is the Difference between a Group of Musicians and a Team of Engineering Students?

A Philosophical Approach to the Problem-Based Nature of Engineering

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ABSTRACT

Analogies between the group dynamics of a music ensemble and the general case of teamwork have been a recurring theme in management philosophy. The author of this paper has previously examined such analogies critically in connection with his own research concerning the actual patterns of decision-making in a music performance. One conclusion from this research is that these patterns are, to a large extent, generalizable to decision-making in other group contexts. At the same time, however, analogies always “hide” and “highlight” certain aspects of what they are meant to say something about (to repurpose vocabulary from George Lakoff & Mark Johnson’s *Metaphors We Live By* [1]). Exploring the limits of an analogy may consequently lead to a clearer idea of the special traits of each of the two compared entities. This paper uses the critical examination of an analogy between a small music ensemble (such as a rock band) and a team of engineering students to emphasize where the two fundamentally differ in their decision-making patterns. At a first glance, the way musicians base their actions in a performance on a combination of goals (broadly construed), expectations for the actions of others, internalized routines, and prior communication with exact agreements, is very close to that of a team of engineering students. Where the two differ is especially in the way goals emerge and are negotiated in a group. Engineering processes tend to be problem-based, and problems can be discussed differently (and often more constructively) than a musical idea.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This paper sets out to critically explore an analogy between a team of engineering students and a composing music ensemble, such as a rock band. By comparing the two types of collaboration, which, it will be argued, have many similarities, important differences between the two can be identified, and thereby lead towards a different way of explaining what distinguishes the work process of engineering teams. Critical reflection on the analogy – rather than the analogy in itself – thus provides a pedagogical tool for making engineering students understand the nature of their (coming) profession.

Engineering disciplines are typically regarded as inherently tied to problem-based work. Even if a university offering engineering programs does not explicitly brand these studies as being “problem-based”, they will usually still have an emphasis on teamwork and collaborative projects revolving around a ‘real-life’ context (see e.g. [2] and [3]). Making engineering students understand the problem-based character of their disciplines is, however, complicated by several factors. First, there is a strong weight within the specific educations on subject-specific learning, e.g. the learning goals shared between chemical engineering and chemistry as a natural science education, between computer engineering and computer science etc. How does one make engineering students understand how their studies go beyond this type of learning goals? Second, problem-based learning is not limited to engineering (as witnessed by the fact that Aalborg University uses a PBL model throughout all of their educations [4]). So what characterizes the particular way engineers base their endeavors on problems (i.e. as opposed to the general contextualization of a topic that most educations are able to do)? On the way to answering these questions, it is worth comparing the field of engineering to another field concerned with construction or development in a general sense, but not necessarily with formulated problems. One such field is a composing music ensemble.

Analogies between the group dynamics of a music ensemble and the general case of teamwork have been a recurring theme in various fields concerned with leadership, organizational structures and management in general (witness e.g. [5] and [6] and [7])). The analogy is, however, not entirely neutral (nor are analogies in general, see section 2 below). For instance, focusing on cues for good leadership in the context of a music ensemble implies an understanding of the latter as having a specific kind of organizational structure with a leader. This is not necessarily the case, as the author of the present paper has argued in previous research [8]. There are, however, if we look at teamwork in general, several interesting things that can be generalized from the way musicians interact to group interaction in general, thus also including the interaction of a group of engineering students, and in some cases even provide an ideal for such interaction.

The way musicians base their actions in a performance on a combination of goals (broadly construed), expectations for the actions of others, internalized routines, and

prior communication with exact agreements, has a detailed parallel in a team of engineering students (and graduated engineers for that matter). Furthermore, in terms of knowledge management – a booming field in management in general, but especially in relation to engineering enterprises (see e.g. [9] and [10]) – the community of musicians, whether groups, teachers, or students, demonstrate highly evolved skills in handling (communicating as well as preserving) not only explicit knowledge, but also the practical know-how sometimes referred to as “tacit knowledge” (see section 5).

Again, exactly because of the limits of any analogy, it is worth considering where the two compared entities – a music ensemble on the one hand, and a team of engineering students on the other – differ from each other. A particular difference this paper emphasizes (in section 6), relates to the way ideas (broadly construed) are negotiated in the group prior to taking action based on these ideas. In fact, this may be a crucial aspect of the work of an engineer.

The author of this paper currently works with first-year engineering students at Aalborg University Esbjerg (henceforth AAUE), as teacher of a cross-curricular PBL course on the first semester and co-supervisor of several student projects in the second semester, across 5 different engineering programs. The author has, however, previously specialized (within his career as a philosopher) in the development of theoretical models for explaining interpersonal coordination in context of music ensembles. It has therefore been a natural step to consider whether some of the insights gained via the latter research could find relevance in context of coordination processes in engineering teams.

2 ANALOGIES – A SHORT SWOT ANALYSIS

This paper uses the term “analogy” as covering explicit comparisons of two, in practice, normally unrelated entities or situations, which serve to say something about at least one of the two compared entities or situations.

Employing an analogy is of course not the only way to get a point across. In order to evaluate analogies (and the discussion thereof) as a pedagogical tool, one approach could be to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the tool – or what is popularly known as a “SWOT analysis” (a discussion of the emergence and development of SWOT analysis as a concept can be found in [11]).

The strength of analogies is the pedagogical potential: one may actually be able to get a point across more clearly via reference to a context the listener is more familiar with.

On the other hand, a weakness of analogies is the possible lack of precision: There can be a thin line between analogy and poetic metaphor, and the latter is typically meant to be ambiguous, with artistic purposes. Worse, analogies can sometimes purport to be actual models of whatever they are trying to say something about. This is problematic because analogies *highlight* certain similarities between the two

compared entities, but at the same time *hide* certain differences. The terms “highlight” and “hide” are directly borrowed from George Lakoff and Mark Johnson’s work on the implicit, structural metaphors underlying daily language. One of Lakoff and Johnson’s examples is the metaphor “time is money”, which underlies several expressions such as “spending time”, “using/wasting time”, “thank you for your time”, “not having enough time” and so on [1]. This metaphor highlights a correlation between a certain period of time and the possibility of making money within this time, but hides the fact that time is something abstract and by its own definitions an ongoing process, beyond our direct control. Analogies, being, in a way, explicit structural metaphors, are subject to the same kind of pitfalls.

When we examine what a given analogy highlights or hides, however, there is a strong potential – an opportunity – for learning about the nature of the two compared entities. This is how we will approach the analogy presented in the next section: as an opportunity for learning about both sides of the analogy, even though we are doing so with the purpose of eventually showcasing properties of one of the two compared entities.

A threat to any analogy is that it is deemed too inaccurate to be useful, but this should be of little significance here, as we are, exactly, searching for such inaccuracies, in order to learn from them.

3 A ROCK BAND AND A TEAM OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS: INTRODUCING AN ANALOGY

Music ensembles and engineering teams come in different shapes and sizes. Apart from the number of people in a group, the limits of the interaction are also defined by the specific line of work, e.g., for music ensembles, the piece of music or genre, on which an eventual performance is based, and for an engineering team, e.g. which discipline (building and construction, chemical, electrical, computer, mechanical or other type of engineering) or specific project the team is affiliated with. Instead of fleshing out the many interesting nuances of the way music ensembles and engineering teams may work, we will consider the more specific analogy of, on the one hand, a rock band playing original material, and on the other, a project team of engineering students. The purpose of this restriction is to give the “ensemble analogy” the strongest possible presentation, in order to more clearly pinpoint where the crucial differences between musicians and engineers lie.

When we talk about a rock band playing original material, we think of a group of typically 3-6 people, playing music they have composed themselves. The task of composing may be dominated by one or more people, or done in an actual act of collaboration between band members.

By a project team of engineering students, we understand a team of engineering students in any semester, consisting, typically, of 3-6 students, working on a project of their own choice. The actual formulation and delineation of the problem, on which the project is based, conceptually, can be a more or less democratic process, but for

the purposes of the analogy that follows, we assume that the members actually collaborate in this respect.

Before we turn to the central issue of creative development, whether leading to a composition or a finished engineering project, we will start by having a look at collaboration in general in the two compared cases, and how it is organized.

4 ORGANIZATION AND COORDINATION IN MUSIC ENSEMBLES AND ENGINEERING TEAMS

In previous research [8], the author has argued that the organization processes of a music ensemble may differ drastically, depending on the level of organization: At rehearsal level, an ensemble such as a symphony orchestra often has limited time to master a piece prior to a performance. In such a rehearsal, there is no time for long discussions among the musicians. Instead, a conductor or other leader manages the rehearsal in an autocratic manner. At a more general, organizational level, however, e.g. when deciding which pieces to play, which soloists to book, everyday logistics etc., even an entire symphony orchestra could potentially (and does, in many concrete cases, see e.g. [12]) take part in the discussions, thus mirroring a democratic process. At the other side of the rehearsal, the level of performance, musicians (as well as their conductors, if any) are rarely able to discuss anything (there may be various types of verbal or non-verbal signals integrated in the performance that help communicate urgent messages – see [13] for examples – but seldom an actual conversation in the traditional sense). Viewed in isolation, the music performance is almost a kind of anarchist society, where every person shares the responsibility of trying to coordinate with everyone else playing. Because, however, the rehearsal level affects the performance, and because the musicians often have a strong sense of ‘how things should be’ in relation to a piece of music or a genre, the music performance is not simply a case of unchallenged personal freedom.

The aforementioned three levels of organization have special properties in the rock band. The transition between the general, organizational level and the rehearsal level is often fluid: Because the band is a much smaller unit than e.g. a symphony orchestra, quick, ad hoc communication about other issues than the music can happen swiftly without interrupting the workflow much. Live performance has the same character for the rock band as for the symphony orchestra of being a normatively conditioned situation where everyone shares responsibility for maintaining a coherent output. Studio performance (borrowing a term from [14]) on the other hand, shaping a definitive version of a piece of music for wide distribution in recorded form, typically has a structure similar to that of a rehearsal, where the band can stop, discuss, change things and continue as they see fit. Finally, the rehearsal itself can be very different from that of a classical ensemble, small or large, in that the composition on which an eventual performance is based is not always a pre-established entity. When the band is working on new material, regardless of how many of the band members have actual input for the composition, the band is not

simply learning how the piece should be played, but trying, more fundamentally, to figure out what the piece is, what it consists of, what they want it to be.

The music performance and the coordination processes taking place therein is a field of inquiry in itself (see e.g. [15]), but in general, musicians have the following ‘tools’ at hand when coordinating their actions with those of other musicians in a performance (these are in line with [16]): There are the context-specific norms taken for granted by the musician as being commonly accepted – these especially depend on verbal agreements made in advance with the other musicians (or instructions given by a conductor during rehearsal). There are the expectations the musician may have for the actions of others, expectations based e.g. on how the others have typically behaved before – how they are likely to interpret a certain kind of phrase, if they tend to play a bit too loud or too quiet, accelerate or slow down etc. Finally, there is of course also the possibility of coordinating by swiftly adjusting to the visible or audible behavior of others. Instances of all of the above can be found in the interaction of a (composing) rock band, although one might expect the musicians to be particularly proficient in coordinating according to pre-established norms understood as common knowledge in the band, given that they have built the music they are playing together.

Turning to the team of engineering students, it may be difficult to find a clear parallel to the music performance as a delineated situation. There may, however, be many situations where the students are, in practice, working together without much verbal communication, relying on what they understand as commonly accepted goals and strategies in the team. As such, daily interaction in the engineering team mirrors that of the rehearsal or studio recording process of a rock band: there can, most certainly, be agreements with respect to how work is distributed in the group, which can focus work in the team around a few types of activities at the time, but a bit of back and forth between being quietly “in flow” (to apply the popular terminology of [17]) together and having discussions about how to proceed, is unavoidable.

For both the rock band and the team of engineering students, many power structures are possible, ranging from having one, strict leader of the group, to negotiating all decisions with everyone in the group. The author’s personal experience as a teacher and co-supervisor of first year engineering students is that most student teams are hybrids, management-wise: Typically, one or more people in a group take on the role of ‘chairman’, moderating the discussions, but not necessarily monopolizing decisions – i.e. in many situations, such a group will have a democratic process, where everyone in the group is heard, before making a decision. The same type of management is possible in the rock band, but in practice, for reasons we will return to in the next two sections, democratic processes may sometimes end up feeling forced or superficial, and in the worst case, escalating into a hostile working climate. (Conversely, these scenarios could also, potentially, occur in an engineering environment.)

All in all, we may easily find parallels between a rock band and any other small collaborating team when we consider how work in general is organized, irrespective of what the work actually consists in. Once we consider the organization of the content of the work situation, however, the comparisons become less trivial, as we shall see in the next section.

5 KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT – TACIT AND EXPLICIT

Recent decades have seen an increased focus on knowledge management in businesses in general, prompted by a shift towards considering the knowledge e.g. a company produces, acquires or maintains (e.g. with respect to effective procedures for whatever the company does) as central to the survival of the company on the market (see e.g. [18]), rather than focusing on the – in nature, often fluctuating – sales numbers. This focus is also reflected in engineering practices (see [8] and [9]), and to some extent in engineering educations: For instance, teams of engineering students at AAUE are taught basic knowledge management tools such as formulating goals and plans for their mutual learning processes, and following up on how well they met these goals, to which extent a plan was followed etc. Where engineering practices see a major challenge, however, is in the management of so-called *tacit knowledge*, i.e. all the practical and, at least initially, non-verbalized knowhow, built by employees via experience with concrete situations.

Some approaches to tacit knowledge management (see e.g. [19]) rely on tacit knowledge eventually becoming explicit knowledge (e.g. by nudging employees to explain what they are doing), a strategy that may work for some instances, while others (see e.g. [20]) use video and other types of multimedia for essentially maintaining “watch and learn” databases, offering a digital alternative to a craft’s apprenticeship. All of these approaches still ‘early days’ in an engineering context. Engineering students in particular, typically do not have formal procedures for handling tacit knowledge, but regard it as a natural part of the practical work, a part they are not required to account for.

What is interesting, however, is that if we turn to music ensembles, and in fact, musicians in general, knowledge management (although it is rarely conceived of as such) already includes detailed practices for handling, broadly speaking, tacit knowledge: A violinist may show another violinist how a particular passage should be bowed or phrased. Sometimes there is an established vocabulary for referring to particular types of bowing or phrasing, other times it requires an illustration. A pianist may be asked to use his or her imagination in order to play something as if they were in a particular time, place or emotional situation (see e.g. the workshops described in [21] and the account of working with David Bowie in [22]). A band working on a new song may have to try something out, listen to it and make a decision about whether to change something – a process that has strongly tacit elements, but at the same time has a logical, “trial and error”-like flow that makes sure the band works towards an optimal ‘product’ or compromise (although there is no guarantee they will reach one). Many more examples could be given, but the general thing to note here is that

referring to, inspiring access to or otherwise communicating tacit knowledge is a commonly accepted part of music practices.

In the author's opinion, however, one of the reasons for the tacit dimension being an accepted condition of a musician's work is that it is commonly accepted that there are parts of this work, which cannot be put into exact words. This has a downside, because, unlike in an engineering team, decisions or instructions (e.g. from a band leader, if there is one) are sometimes accepted or forced with no preceding arguments for a decision (other than e.g. some vague statement of 'visions' for the music). In a band with less democratic practices for development of a composition, it is not an atypical scenario that the musician initiating a composition process will feel the right to veto decisions in accordance with his or her ideas for what the music should sound like. And if the other musicians do not acknowledge this right, conflicts ensue that, again, can be difficult to resolve, due to the lack of a tradition for explicit arguments for different solutions.

In the next, and penultimate section, we will discuss how the (understandable) lack of tradition for arguments in relation to basic musical ideas provides slight, but important differences between the creative processes of a rock band and a team of engineering students.

6 ON CREATIVE PROCESSES AND WHY AN INITIATING PROBLEM MAKES A DIFFERENCE

Engineering teams base their work on problems they are trying to address and solve, or at least contribute to solving. At Aalborg University Esbjerg, engineering students are, among other tools for the ideation process, provided with the so-called 6W diagram, which gives them an overview of the phases a problem analysis needs to go through. The exact order of the "6 Ws" may differ, and consequently the diagram arranges these in a circle around the term "Problem", but the content remains the same:

Problem: The process begins with an initiating problem of a form such as "how can it be that...?", "how do we make X better with respect to...?", "how do we solve the problem with...?" This initiating problem, represented by the center of the diagram, is analyzed with respect to various aspects that can be summarized as answering 6 questions (all including the letter W):

What exactly constitutes the problem? In this connection, the students are encouraged to bring forth more specific details on the nature of the problem, scientific background material etc.

Why is it a problem? Here, the broader, e.g. societal relevance of the problem is investigated further.

Who are the stakeholders?

Where and **when** is the problem relevant/present? These questions should inspire the students to find concrete examples, preferably from real life.

How can the problem be solved? The student is prompted to think in terms of possible strategies. This eventually leads to a solution process, where one solution strategy is chosen and further delineated based on available resources (time, money, materials, man power etc.)

Once a solution is planned, it is carried out and evaluated, after which point further improvements can be made. The improved version can be subject to new evaluation, and the team can go through as many cycles of improvement and evaluation as they find relevant or possible within the given time frame.

If we turn to the creative process of a rock band working on a new piece of music, certain interpretations of the 6 questions above might make sense:

What is the piece of music like? Which notes, rhythms, overall structure etc.?

Why work on this particular musical idea? And why should it have a particular structure?

Who should the piece appeal to? Should any other musicians be taken onboard for a recording?

Where should the piece be played or recorded? On which platforms should it be released first?

When should it be played or released?

How is the performance or recording going to be carried out? Are there difficulties that may ensue? Things that need to be revised in the piece to make it playable for the musicians?

The major difference from the 6W diagram in engineering, however, is the absence of a formal problem initiating the creative process. In its place is, instead, something like a musical 'idea' or 'gestalt' that the musicians are trying to actualize in their performance. In some cases, it may be in the process of figuring out how to play the piece that they become aware of how its underlying ideas could be characterized – in other words, the musicians compose the piece in an act of performance similar to improvisation. In other cases, a musician has a rough idea of a composition that he or she brings to the table for the entire band to collaborate on. This situation is where things can become problematic, as hinted in section 5: If the rest of the band does not acknowledge a special connection between the initiator of a composition process and the 'essence' of the piece of music, conflicts will very likely take place. In other words, the musicians often lack a joint capability of evaluating their answers to the 6 W questions, because they do not necessarily share access equally to the initiating 'vision', against which their endeavors are being measured.

This does not necessarily mean that a music ensemble such as a rock band is necessarily less democratic than an engineering team, nor should one make a romantic claim that a democratic work process is a hindrance to the creation of great, coherent art: Musicians *could* potentially be lucky enough to be on the same page with respect to the overarching ideas for the music, and pieces composed in a

manner similar to improvisation can also have great artistic value. Conversely, engineering students, may, in spite of what they have been taught, experience toxic group dynamics where one or a few people in the team take full control, without wanting to justify all of their decisions. Engineering students could also be (and are sometimes) working in a pseudo-problem-based manner, where they start from a practical solution they favor, and work their way backwards to a justification for the solution, in shape of a traditional problem analysis. If, however, we look at the conceptual pre-conditions for their creative processes, it does seem as if engineering students have a much better starting point for actual, democratic collaboration in their creative process.

7 CONCLUSION

An analogy comparing a team of engineering students to a rock band may be of help in explaining and providing nuance to a discussion of

- the many possible variations on how a unit may be organized, opening up the minds of e.g. engineering students to more than one fixed organizational structure
- how interpersonal coordination takes place – which may be useful in showing students the virtues they should strive for in order to avoid conflicts
- how knowledge management can include all aspects of the team's knowledge, including tacit ones, broadly conceived

An important limit of the analogy lies in the difference between how the creative process is typically initiated, and the consequences this has for whether informed, collaborative decisions can be made.

Incidentally, Karl Popper [23] suggested “piecemeal social engineering” as an ideal form of governmental practice, working pragmatically to find the best possible solutions to delineated problems, rather than striving to make decisions in accordance with an overarching ideology and its grand visions for the future. In continuation of this, it is interesting to note how the engineering team in itself represents a possible ideal for democratic collaboration in the way it addresses and works with problems.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lakoff, G. and Johnson, M. (1980), *Metaphors We Live By*, Chicago University Press, Chicago, pp. 7-13

[2] SDU (2019). Engineering Programmes, webpage for University of Southern Denmark's engineering programmes,
 URL: <https://www.sdu.dk/en/uddannelse/ingenioer> (accessed August 2, 2019).

[3] Gaber, A. (2019), Students hone engineering, teamwork skills by tackling real-world projects, *YaleNews*, February 12, 2019, online news from Yale University,
 URL: <https://news.yale.edu/2019/02/12/students-hone-engineering-teamwork-skills-tackling-real-world-projects> (accessed August 2, 2019)

[4] Aalborg University PBL Academy (2019), About, webpage, URL:
<https://www.pbl.aau.dk/about-the-pbl-academy/> (accessed April 30, 2019).

[5] Mantere, S., Sillince, J. A. A. and Hämmäläinen, V. (2007), Music as a metaphor for organizational change, *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, Vol. 20, No. 3, pp. 447-459.

[6] Trouche, L. and Drijvers, P. (2008), From artifacts to instruments: a theoretical framework behind the orchestra metaphor, *Research on Technology and the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics*, Vol. 2, Cases and perspectives, pp. 363-392.

[7] Copenhagen Business School (2009), Art & Leadership and CBS Leadership Lab, webpage, URL: <https://www.cbs.dk/node/233766> (accessed April 30, 2019).

[8] Frimodt-Møller, S. R. (2011), The Musical Workplace: A Music Philosopher's Approach to the Role of Individual Decision-Making in Group Coordination, *Philosophy of Management*, Vol. 10, No. 3, pp. 25-40.

[9] Hao, J., Zhao, Q., Yan, Y. and Wang, G. (2017), A Review of Tacit Knowledge: Current Situation and the Direction to Go, *International Journal of Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering*, Vol. 27, pp. 727-741.

[10] Frimodt-Møller, S. R. (2018), Towards a Taxonomy of Tacit Knowing in Context of Project-Oriented Problem-Based Learning in the Engineering Sciences, 7th

International Research Symposium on PBL: Innovation, PBL and Competences in Engineering Education, Sunyu, W., Kolmos, A., Guerra, A. and Weifeng, Q. (eds.), Aalborg Universitetsforlag, pp. 440-449

[11] Madsen, D. Ø. (2016), SWOT Analysis: A Management Fashion Perspective, *International Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 39-56.

[12] Wagner, R. J. and Ward, T. (2002), Explorations of Teamwork: The Lahti Symphony Orchestra, *Harmony – Forum of the Symphony Orchestra Institute*, Vol. 15, online publication, URL: https://iml.esm.rochester.edu/polyphonic-archive/wp-content/uploads/sites/13/2012/03/Lahti_Wagner_Ward.pdf (accessed April 30, 2019)

[13] Frimodt-Møller, S. R. (2010), Playing by the Rules? A Philosophical Approach to Normativity and Coordination in Music Performance, PhD dissertation, Institute of Philosophy, Education and the Study of Religions, University of Southern Denmark, URL: www.orkesterfilosofi.dk/DissertationMay2010.pdf (accessed August 2, 2019), pp. 36-37.

[14] Davies, S. (2001). *Musical Works and Performances: A Philosophical Exploration*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, pp. 5-8 (and throughout the book).

[15] Frimodt-Møller, S. R. (2010), Playing by the Rules? A Philosophical Approach to Normativity and Coordination in Music Performance, PhD dissertation, Institute of Philosophy, Education and the Study of Religions, University of Southern Denmark, URL: www.orkesterfilosofi.dk/DissertationMay2010.pdf (accessed August 2, 2019), pp. 1-23.

[16] Frimodt-Møller, S. R. (2010), Playing by the Rules? A Philosophical Approach to Normativity and Coordination in Music Performance, PhD dissertation, Institute of Philosophy, Education and the Study of Religions, University of Southern Denmark, URL: www.orkesterfilosofi.dk/DissertationMay2010.pdf (accessed August 2, 2019), pp. 226-239.

[17] Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1990), *Flow: The Psychology of Optimal Experience*, Harper and Row, New York.

[18] Nonaka, I., and Takeuchi, H. (1995), *The Knowledge-Creating Company: How Japanese Companies Create the Dynamics of Innovation*, Oxford University Press, Oxford.

[19] Penciu, D., Abel, M.-H. and Van Den Abeele, D. (2013), A Workspace to Manage Tacit Knowledge Contributing to Railway Product Development during Tendering, Knowledge Discovery, Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management. Second International Joint Conference, IC3K 2010, Valencia, Spain, October 25-28, 2010. Revised Selected Papers, Fred, A., Dietz, J.L.G., Liu, K., Filipe, J. (eds.), Springer, *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, Vol. 272, pp. 399-412.

[20] Stapleton, L., Smith, D. and Murphy, F. (2005), Systems engineering methodologies, tacit knowledge and communities of practice, *AI and Society*, Vol. 19, pp. 159-180.

[21] Westney, W. (2019), The Un-Masterclass: What Is It?, webpage for commercially offered workshop, URL: <http://williamwestney.com/the-un-master-class/> (accessed April 30, 2019).

[22] Cope, C. (2016), Jordan Rudess of Dream Theater on working with David Bowie and new album 'The Astonishing', *Drowned in Sound*, online publication, February 8, 2016, URL: http://drownedinsound.com/in_depth/4149776-jordan-rudess-of-dream-theater-on-working-with-david-bowie-and-new-album-the-astonishing (accessed April 30, 2019).

[23] Popper, K. R. (1945), *The Open Society and Its Enemies*. Vol.1: The Spell of Plato, George Routledge & Sons, Ltd., London, pp. 15-28.